

Chemotaxonomic study of fruit cuticular waxes of the genus *Chaenomeles* Lindl. introduced plants

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Fruit cuticular waxes cause the surface hydrophobic properties, which limits transpiration (Müller & Riederer, 2005). In addition, the epicuticular waxes functions elucidated to date include regulating plant interactions with insects (Rebora et al., 2020) and pathogens (Łażniewska et al., 2012), as well as participating in the fruit formation and ripening processes (Trivedi et al., 2019).

The aim of our study was to identify species-specific features of the fruit cuticular waxes component composition of the genus *Chaenomeles* Lindl. introduced plants, resistant to steppe climate conditions.

The objects of the study conducted in 2021 were the fruits of the plants *Ch. japonica*, *Ch. speciosa*, *Ch. cathayensis*, *Ch. × superba*, and *Ch. × californica*. Ripe fruits were selected from mid-September to the third decade of October, depending on the fruit ripening time of each species.

The prepared chloroform extracts of fruit cuticular waxes differed in their dry matter content (Table 1).

Table 1. Dry matter content ($\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) in fruit cuticular wax extracts of the genus *Chaenomeles* introduced plants ($x \pm \text{SD}$, $n = 5$, $P < 0.05$)

Plant species	<i>Ch. japonica</i>	<i>Ch. speciosa</i>	<i>Ch. cathayensis</i>	<i>Ch. × superba</i>	<i>Ch. × californica</i>
Concentration of extract, $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$	$207,6 \pm 12,3^a$	$397,6 \pm 10,4^b$	$281,4 \pm 13,6^c$	$310,2 \pm 10,9^c$	$302,4 \pm 14,2^c$

Note. Different letters in a row indicate statistically significant differences in the means of the pair being compared (according to the Tukey test).

The GC-MS method was used to determine the wax chemical composition and content (in % of the total) of the individual components. Chromatographic profiles of the fruit cuticular waxes extracts of the genus *Chaenomeles* species and hybrids differed in some qualitative and quantitative characteristics for individual constituents, but had a similar distribution of chemical compounds (Fig. 1).

In total, 68 chemical compounds were identified in the cuticular waxes of the fruits of all *Chaenomeles* species and hybrids studied. The bulk of these compounds belonged to five chemical classes (fatty acids, aldehydes, alcohols, alkanes, and esters), while a group of minor compounds combined the terpenes, terpenoids, and other derivatives.

Analysis of the results of the phytochemicals GC-MS identification showed variability in the ratio of chemical classes in the cuticular waxes of *Chaenomeles* fruit (Fig. 2).

Fig. 1. Typical chromatogram of chloroform extracts of the fruit cuticular waxes of the genus *Chaenomeles* plants with the main components: 1 – 9-decenoic acid, 2 – hexadecanoic acid, 3 – heptacosanal, 4 – 9-hexadecenal, 5 – undecenoic acid tetradecyl ester, 6 – diisooctyl phthalate, 7 – heptacosanal, 8 – tricosanal, 9 – hexatriacontane, 10 – olean-12-ene-3,28-diol, 11 – 1-gentetracontanol

Fig. 2. Relative content (% of the sum) of the compounds of different chemical classes in fruit cuticular waxes of the genus *Chaenomeles* plants

The largest number of components (37 compounds) was found in *Ch. japonica* fruit waxes, 30 compounds in *Ch. × superba* waxes, 28 in *Ch. speciosa* waxes, 23 compounds in *Ch. × californica* waxes, and 21 compounds in *Ch. cathayensis* fruit waxes. The content of unidentified compounds ranged from 2.6% (in the fruit waxes of *Ch. × californica*) to 8.2% of the sum of all compounds (in the waxes of *Ch. × superba* fruits).

The averaged results of the fruit waxes composition of *Chaenomeles* species and hybrids indicate that the largest share (38.8% of the total) was accounted for by aldehydes, 22% of the total was occupied by alkanes, 15.2% – by fatty acid esters, 14.9% was occupied by alcohols, and the smallest shares were occupied by fatty acids (4.9% of the total) and terpenes together with terpenoids and other derivatives (3.9% of the total).

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